

Fuel Tank Fastener Sparking: Development of a Threshold Database and the Benefits of Computational Electromagnetics Simulation for Certification

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1. ABSTRACT

Prevention of catastrophic effects due to fuel vapor ignition is a key part of any aircraft certification effort. One potential fuel vapor ignition source is arcing and sparking resulting from lightning currents conducted through airframe components, such as fasteners and joints. The most common method of demonstrating adequate ignition source prevention involves extensive testing of a large variety of fasteners and fastener configurations. Fastener test levels are based on current densities distributed throughout the aircraft, obtained through full-vehicle lightning testing and simulation.

The fastener design handbook [4] contains a sample of the testing and simulation effort used to identify potential ignition sources in fuel tanks. Findings and data published in the project reports handbook serve as baseline engineering evaluation for industry to reduce the overall quantity of tests required during the fuel tank design process. Several factors were studied for their impact on fastener non-sparking thresholds. There are three phases associated with this study.

Phase 1 of this project focused on developing a public fastener database for non-sparking thresholds due to conducted lightning currents in coupon level tests representing metal fuel tanks. This included both nominal and faulted fastener installations.

Phase 2 involved the development of a metal fuel tank lightning design handbook and was carried out by EMA. The focus of this phase was to demonstrate how lightning environments could be established in aircraft fuel systems using validated numerical simulations.

Phase 3 of this project focused on developing a public fastener database for lightning non-sparking thresholds in coupon level tests in carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) fuel tanks for both nominal and faulted fastener installations.

This paper provides the background for the project, findings of each phase of this study, and opportunities for future work. All work done during this project is publically available to be used as a design guide. This project was funded by KART grants and done in partnership with EMA.

2. ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

3D CEM – Three Dimensional Computational Electromagnetic

ARP – Aerospace Recommended Practices

AWG – American Wire Gauge

CAD – Computer Aided Design

CFR – Code of Federal Regulations

CFRP – Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic

DC – Direct Current

DEL – Direct Effects of Lightning

EM – Electro Magnetic

EMA – Electro Magnetic Applications Inc.

EMA3D – Commercially available 3D CEM software

FDTD - Finite Difference Time Domain

IVD – Ion Vapor Deposition

kA – Kilo Amperes

KART – Kansas Aviation Research Technology growth initiative group

NIAR – National Institute for Aviation Research

OEM – Original Equipment Manufacturer

TA's – Test Articles

3. BACKGROUND

Due to the flammable nature of the fuel vapors in aircraft, it is critical to show that the fuel vapors will not ignite due to a lightning event. This was previously done by showing compliance to 14 CFR 25.981 through extensive testing programs. The §25.981 rule covered all fuel related ignition sources, including lightning. As it was written, aircraft manufacturers had to show dual fault tolerance for lightning ignition sources. The FAA found the application of the rule as written was impractical and drove applicants to certify through the use of special conditions or exemptions [1]. Because of this, the portion of §25.981 addressing lightning was replaced by §25.954, which states that fuel ignition must be extremely improbable with respect to failures within the fuel system, flammability, and critical lightning strikes [2].

NIAR began a project with EMA through KART grants in 2016-2021 to create a publically available fastener database and wing model in Zone 3 areas of aircraft. The aim of the fastener database was to determine the conducted current test level at which fasteners will produce ignition sources in both metal and composite skins and compile a report to help determine certification paths by identifying potential faults and a testing method. EMA created a numerical wing model to demonstrate a simulation and validation process that could be used to establish the airplane lightning environment as part of the compliance activities outlined in AC 25.954-1[3]. The project reports that resulted from this project are available as resource for industry use to reduce the quantity of engineering evaluation tests required in the early stages of fuel tank design.

The work exemplifies testing and simulation used in combination to reduce the overall effort of compliance with §25.954.

4. PHASE 1 – METAL FUEL TANKS

The details and results of the metal fuel tank analysis can be found in the KART metal fasteners report [4]. The purpose of Phase 1 of this project was to determine the non-sparking thresholds of various fasteners in metal skins experimentally as a result of conducted lightning current. The non-sparking threshold was defined as the maximum test level that did not result in a spark and had to be determined on the first test on a previously untested coupon. A spark as defined in this paper may refer to a voltage discharge across a gap as well as thermal effects causing melting, incandescence, and/or ejection of heated/incandescent material. A number of factors were assessed for their impact on the non-sparking threshold of the fasteners: type of fastener, head type, fastener diameter, fit type, fastener coating, faulted fastener installations, manufacturer variability, and quantity of fasteners per joint. Faulted fasteners were included in the testing both to determine the impact they have on sparking and because it is required to test fault tolerances in §25.954 (a) (1). The test article designs are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 below. Single fastener configurations were tested in order to assess an isolated fastener, but this configuration is not representative of an in-service aircraft. Therefore, the entirety of the single fastener configuration test matrix was duplicated with a quadruple fastener configuration to better represent in-service aircraft installations. A simplified version of the test matrix for the faults can be found in Table 1 below, and the full matrix and threshold values for all fasteners can be found in Table 3 and Table 4 at the end of the paper.

Fig. 1. Schematic of Single Fastener Test Article

Fig. 2. Schematic of a Quadruple Fastener Test Article

Multiple OEMs participated in this phase by supplying test articles manufactured according to their standard processes. This allowed NIAR to determine whether manufacturing variability played a role in the non-sparking thresholds. Upon arriving at NIAR, physical and electrical inspections in the form of visual inspections, paint thickness measurements, and DC resistance measurements across fastener joints were taken and recorded. Testing itself was carried out utilizing the photographic method for ignition source detection per

SAE ARP 5416A [5]. A schematic of the test setup can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the conducted current with the photographic method of ignition source detection test setup

Nominally installed fastener installations were tested first. Differential probes were used to monitor the voltage buildup across each fastened joint. When the measured voltage waveform showed signs of discontinuities on the leading edge, this was often a sign of internal sparking. During the internal sparking event, the fastener head and collar contain the sparks so that the spark event is not detected by the cameras. Internal sparking was monitored as it may indicate the presence of an anomaly in a particular test article. These test articles were tested starting at 10 kA. If a spark was observed (as in Fig. 4), the test level was lowered until the non-sparking threshold was obtained, or a 1 kA test amplitude was reached. If a spark was not observed at 10 kA, no threshold was obtained. A number of factors were assessed for their potential impact on the non-sparking threshold. The type of fastener, head type, fastener diameter, fit type, fastener coating, quantity of fasteners per joint, faulted fastener installations, and manufacturer variability were all varied to form 128 unique configurations.

Fig. 4. Fastener sparking from conducted current

Faulted fastener installations were tested in a second round of testing, which began after testing of nominal fastener installations was complete. All faulted test articles had four fasteners per joint; three were nominal installations and one was a faulted installation. Since many configurations from nominal testing never sparked at 10 kA, it was decided to increase the maximum test level for faulted fastener installations to 100 kA. The increased test amplitude allowed relative comparison between configurations. After consulting with the SAE AE-2 Committee and KART OEMs, the

following fault types were chosen: burrs, scratches in fuel tank primer, under torqued fasteners, gap under head, gap under collar, and an oversized hole. Head type, coating type, and fastener type were still varied in the faulted configuration. The use of sealant was eliminated from testing as the amount of sealant on the fastener is hard to control, the only exception to this were the faulted test articles supplied by OEM 1 which contained sealant [4]. The assembly details for the faulted test articles can be seen in Table 1 below. Testing started at 10 kA for the faulted fasteners with a conductive coating. If no spark was observed, the configuration was tested at incrementally higher levels up to 100 kA. If the configuration did not spark at 100 kA, testing was complete and no threshold was obtained. Testing was capped at 100 kA because it is not likely for fasteners in the fuel tank region to see more than 100 kA of conducted current. Testing on faulted fasteners with a non-conductive coating began at 1 kA and was incrementally increased to 10 kA to determine the non-sparking threshold. The non-sparking threshold for a configuration is defined as the highest test level that did not result in sparking.

Table 1. Fastener assemblies for faulted test articles

No. of Fasteners	Fastener Type	Head Type	Fit Type	No. of Faults Tested
Quad-Fastener	HI-LOK™	Protruding	Transition	6
		Countersink	Transition	6
	HI-LITE™	Protruding	Transition	6
		Countersink	Transition	1
	HI-KOTE/ HI-LOK™	Countersink	Transition	6
	HI-KOTE/ HI-LITE™	Countersink	Transition	6
	Rivet	Protruding	Rivet	6

Fastener coating was the single most significant impact on the non-sparking threshold. According to the data shown in the box-and-whisker plots in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 (the “X” in both figures denotes the average value), titanium fasteners with an IVD coating in aluminum skin – whether they are installed nominally or with faults – will rarely spark at less than 10 kA. Fasteners with a non-conductive coating consistently sparked at or below 10 kA.

Fig. 5. Average Conductive Non-sparking Thresholds

*Note: the test article represented by the green outlier above was not tested above this level. The test article in question did not spark during testing so the threshold may be higher than shown here.

Fig. 6. Average Nonconductive Non-sparking Thresholds

The presence of faulted fasteners did not have a significant impact on the thresholds. Additionally, the DC resistance across each joint, measured prior to and after testing, did not show correlation between the resistance measurements and an external or internal sparking event.

5. PHASE 2 – USING VALIDATED SIMULATIONS TO ESTABLISH FUEL SYSTEM LIGHTNING ENVIRONMENTS IN A METALLIC-SKINNED AIRCRAFT WING

Companies must establish their fuel systems lightning environments when demonstrating compliance to §25.954 (formerly §25.981). Many companies use a combination of testing and simulation to determine conducted current levels and waveforms at appropriate fuel system design feature locations because using testing alone may not be practical. Furthermore, simulations allow for an enhanced understanding of lightning current distributions in aircraft fuel systems and which fundamental EM properties are important to consider for the environment definition. A simulation model capable of characterizing the lightning response of a representative fuel system was developed within the software product EMA3D, a commercially available FDTD CEM tool. A validation exercise is typically required when using numerical analysis for certification. In the validation, the simulation results are compared directly to test results for a representative fuel systems aircraft specimen. Experimental lightning coupling data was obtained by NIAR.

To demonstrate a possible approach to validating simulations, EMA created a numerical model of a wing specimen. The primary steps in this validation process are typically outlined in a validation plan that addresses all modeling and test activities. While no formal validation plan was created for this demonstration, the following areas would typically be addressed within that plan:

1. Identify test specimen(s) that will be used for anchoring the numerical model inputs to the aircraft design.
2. Perform low-level lightning testing on the test specimen at relevant locations.
3. Develop a simulation model to match the test specimen, probe locations, and current entry configurations.
4. Compare the results from testing and the model to establish margins and define where the simulations will be used to establish the lightning environment.
5. Use the validated simulation model to establish any fuel system environment definitions not already addressed during validation activities.

5.1 Test Specimen and Test Plan

The selected test article was a wing that was donated to NIAR for research purposes (shown in Fig. 7). While the structural aspects of the wing were representative of a production aircraft, the specimen was missing the interior fuel system and control surfaces. An internal 4 AWG wire was bonded between the root rib of the wing and Rib 16 to represent a long spanning, low resistance conductor within the wing. Although not identical to fuel pipes, this wire may be representative of a severe bonding configuration for conductors inside the wing. When performing the environment definition process as a part of compliance demonstration, an aircraft manufacturer may need to select a test specimen with other interior fuel systems plumbing. The focus of this study is on structural fasteners and this specimen worked quite well for that purpose, but the process identified here could be expanded to include fuel systems plumbing or other features the specimen might contain. A return array was built around the wing using metallic wires to provide representative current distribution as well as to reduce ground plane effects for the test.

Fig. 7. Donated aircraft wing used as the test specimen for the model validation effort.

The wing in Fig. 7 was instrumented with current probes and B dot probes (used to measure the magnetic fields) for

lightning injection testing which was conducted by NIAR to measure the EM coupling response. Taking safety and feasibility into account, it is typical to inject lower test levels and then scale the results instead of injecting the full-scale test levels into a test article of this size. Three configurations were evaluated where 3 kA of current was injected: wing tip – distributed wing root, leading edge rib – trailing edge bracket, and rib 7 upper fastener near forward spar – wing root upper leading edge. The probes and test configurations are outlined in the test matrix shown below in Table 2. Due to tight construction, it was difficult to implement current probes around interior structural interfaces. Interior B-dot probes on ribs were used to help map interior current distributions on the ribs near high current regions.

Table 2. Test matrix for validation

Test # - Amplitude*	Test Wing Connections		Probe (Type)	# of Probes	Probe Position
	Inj.	Return			
1-3	Wingtip (distributed through 6 braids)	Wing Root (distributed through 6 braids)	Bulk current (Pearson CT)	7	1 attach current 6 detach currents
			Bulk current (Pearson CT)	1	1 pipe (4 AWG wire?) currents
			Magnetic fields (B-dot)	17	7 upper skin locations 6 lower skin locations 4 spar locations
2-3	LE Mount Bracket Attach	TE Mount Bracket Detach	Bulk current (Pearson CT)	2	1 attach current 1 detach current
			Magnetic fields (B-dot)	4	2 upper skin locations 2 lower skin locations
3-3	Rib 7 Fastener	Wing Root Upper TE Side	Bulk current (Pearson CT)	2	1 attach current 1 detach current
			Magnetic fields (B-dot)	11	2 upper skin locations 2 lower skin locations 2 spar locations 5 Rib 7 locations

* For all configurations, the waveform was Comp. A, current level was 3 kA

5.2 Numerical Modeling

The goal of CEM analysis is to capture the pertinent electromagnetic responses of the aircraft being simulated. The model must capture certain features of the aircraft related to resistances, inductances, and capacitances. Starting with the solid body CATIA CAD ensures model components will have accurate dimensions, shapes and locations of the aircraft which relate to the inductive and capacitive EM behavior. Using appropriate material assignments within the model ensures that the resistive portion of the EM effects is captured. The development process of the CEM model involves many details to fully represent the EM aspects of the aircraft design.

The wing model geometry was directly imported from CATIA CAD files. The geometry was appropriately modified to have the necessary component mesh and connectivity. The final wing geometry is shown below in Fig. 9. Certain geometries from the CAD file that do not affect the EM coupling were removed. The return array used for testing was included within the model as shown in Fig 9.

Fig. 8. EMA3D model representing wing geometry

Fig. 9. EMA3D model with return wires around specimen

In addition to having correct geometrical and connectivity representations, incorporating accurate material properties and seam impedances are paramount for having accurate simulations. Some materials, like the aluminum alloys for skins (7150-T7751 and 2024-T3) and spars (7050-T7451), have well defined properties available for lookup in engineering handbooks or specification sheets. These materials are easily defined for this type of model. There are many other features in the aircraft design that must be captured in the CEM model which do not have properties listed in a specification sheet. For these features, laboratory measurements or engineering estimate values are required for the material assignment process. As part of this study, NIAR performed a subset of material characterization testing to determine various fastener contact DC resistance values for this wing. The samples were cut from the opposite wing of the retired aircraft and contained key joints for characterization. A sample coupon for this resistance

characterization is shown in Fig. 10. All primary interfaces between ribs, spars and skins were characterized in this fashion to improve the model fidelity with specifically defined resistances at these locations within the model.

Measurement #	DC Resistance (mΩ)	Side A Thickness	Side B Thickness	Coating	Fastener Count
1	0.177	0.09	0.055	Primer	4
2	0.168	0.055	0.055	Fastener ID	Unique Features
3	0.191	0.06	0.055	HST11-6	Sealant on joint
4	0.167	0.055	0.055	Fastener Diameter (Inch)	
5	0.166	0.09	0.055	.189	
Average	0.1738	0.07	0.055		

Fig. 10. Sample DC resistance measurement results for Rib 7 to upper skin sample.

5.3 Simulation and Test Results Comparison

When performing simulations for certification support, the numerical results must be validated against test results for the aircraft design in question. This validation effort gives confidence that the simulation model accurately determines the lightning response and captures the important EM behavior. Additionally, the validation effort will help to establish margins, or levels of uncertainty that may be applied to the simulation results. Sample comparison waveforms for B-dot and current probes are provided in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

There is a real economic and practical justification to ease the burden of simulation validation and margin development. If reasonable justification and engineering judgement can provide evidence that simulated lightning transients are similar to those acquired from testing, simulations alone will give a legitimate answer to the actual aircraft lightning environment definition. There is no present quantitative margin development approach for lightning transient phenomena provided in industry standards. Once simulation results can qualitatively be shown to provide similar results as test methods, magnitudes on the same order and generally similar waveforms, a standard, easily defined margin, like 6 dB should be accepted by industry.

Fig. 11. Magnetic field comparison on lower skin near Rib 9.

Fig. 12. Interior 4 AWG wire current comparison.

For this study of structural interfaces, all simulation results correlated within 3dB of the experimental measurements as shown for B-dot probes, Fig. 13, and current probes, Fig. 14.

Fig. 13. Full data summary scatter plot for B dot probes

Fig. 14. Bulk current probe scatter plot

One of the significant advantages of simulation is the ability to characterize currents anywhere in the model, especially where physical probes cannot be placed in aircraft configurations. For configurations 2 and 3, current density images were taken of the ribs near the current injection location. Arrows are added within the rib cells to indicate current flow direction around that particular cell. Fig. 15 shows the Rib 7 current density evolution at 6, 30 and 270 μ s. Although the component A injected current peaks near 6 μ s, the current density on the rib does not significantly develop until much later in time, once the lightning current has had time to diffuse through the metallic wing skins. In the 270 μ s capture, the current patterns are quite complex around the neighboring shear ties and both rib posts. These types of current patterns on internal structures can also be beneficial to explore when systems components are mounted to the ribs.

Fig. 15. Current density mapping at varying times on a rib during a fastener strike

5.4 Waveform Reduction and Environment Definition

Test houses should not be responsible for generating all possible waveforms that occur in a lightning event. However, lightning test houses and generators can typically produce the standardized lightning waveforms as identified in SAE ARP 5412B [6]. A reasonable approach to this problem is to convert all transient results (with appropriate applied margins) to standardized waveforms that are typically created by the test house. An important consideration of this waveform conversion is the rise time and action integral associated with the waveform. It would be reasonable to perform a waveform

reduction to find equivalent waveforms for test houses to inject on the coupon samples. SAE ARP 5415B [7] contains explanations of how to perform waveform reduction and this exercise is not included as part of this project.

This final waveform reduction step on actual simulated or measured environments is critical when comparing to the sparking thresholds identified in Phase 1 of this study. It is the link between the actual transient (plus margin) to the sparking threshold that will verify if the aircraft design tolerates the expected lightning environment for that feature.

5.5 Modeling Conclusion

The validation process outlined in Phase 2 of this study demonstrates how an applicant might approach environment definition using validated simulations. There are many cost, informational, and programmatic benefits when incorporating simulations into the compliance demonstration process. For further reading on the process and results of Phase 2, please refer to the wing report contained in Appendix A of the KART metal fastener report [4].

6. PHASE 3 – POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE FUEL TANKS

The final phase of this project looked at the non-sparking thresholds of fasteners installed in CFRP skins and was summarized in the KART composite fastener report [8]. There were a number of variables for this phase, including head type, fastener type, fault type, and skin joint type (CFRP only or CFRP-aluminum hybrid). See Table 3 and Table 5 and the end of the paper for the full test matrix and threshold values. Fault configurations in this phase differed slightly from those in Phase 1. The scratch, under torque, and burr faults remained the same as Phase 1, but gap under head and gap under collar were replaced by an out-of-perpendicularity fault, defined as a fastener being installed four degrees out of perpendicular. In this phase, the substitute Hi-Kote fault was added to the test matrix. This fault had one of the four nominal (conductive) IVD coated fasteners per joint replaced with a (nonconductive) Hi-Kote fastener. Upon intake, test articles were inspected and the paint thickness and DC resistance measurements across the joints were recorded.

Testing began at a peak current Component A amplitude level of 10 kA. If a spark was observed, the test level was incrementally lowered until the non-sparking threshold was obtained. If no sparking was observed at 10 kA, the test level was incrementally increased until the non-sparking threshold was obtained.

An issue that occurred during testing was the abundance of contact sparking and edge glow on the composite coupons themselves. The edges of the test articles contained fuel tank primer only but were not sealed, and there were exposed strips that had no primer. The exposed edges created a visible glow during the conducted current testing, which would cause the test articles to fail the photographic method [9]. Since this study was concerned specifically with fastener thresholds, the threat of an ignition source from edge glow was deemed to fall outside the scope of the project. Opaque black tape was used to cover the coupon edges such that any edge glow and contact sparking present would not be visible to the cameras. See Fig. 16 below for an image of tape application.

Fig. 16. Tape used to hide edge glow from the cameras field of view

The results of testing in Phase 3 showed that fastener coatings have the most significant impact on the non-sparking threshold, which is in line with the results of Phase 1. Phase 3 also showed the type of joint plays a significant role in the sparking threshold. As seen in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18, hybrid carbon-aluminum joints on average had higher non-sparking thresholds than carbon-carbon joints.

Fig. 17. Impact of Joint Type on Protruding Head Fastener Non-sparking Thresholds

Fig. 18. Impact of Joint Type on Countersink Head Fastener Non-sparking Thresholds

The test matrix was designed with the assumption that countersink fasteners represented external heads of skin fasteners and all internal fastener heads would be protruding. For this reason, head side sparking was only considered a failure on fasteners with a protruding head. Shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20 below, when comparing countersink to protruding fasteners, the fault that had the largest change in threshold

value was the perpendicularity fault, followed by nominal installations.

Fig. 19. Non-sparking Thresholds of Protruding Fasteners by Fault Type

Fig. 20. Non-sparking Thresholds of Countersink Fasteners by Fault Type

7. CONCLUSIONS

Phase 1 showed that the presence of faults does not heavily affect the non-sparking threshold of fasteners installed in metal skins, but the coating applied to the fasteners can lower the non-sparking threshold by an order of magnitude.

Phase 2 showed that complex simulations can model the current distribution and EM coupling responses due to lightning transients in metal structures with high fidelity. The results of these models can be used to augment the result of testing in a verification program, and vice versa.

Phase 3 demonstrated that fasteners installed in CFRP or hybrid skins spark at lower levels of conducted current and confirmed that the fastener coating plays an important role in the non-sparking threshold of the fasteners. For development and/or certification testing of fasteners, all exposed CFRP edges should be sealed or painted to contain the edge glow phenomena.

The data and findings of all three phases of this project are available to the public upon request to be used as a design guide for OEMs. The metals report contains all the fastener information and thresholds from metal fastener testing as well as the wing model report [4]. The composite report similarly contains all CFRP and hybrid fastener configuration details and threshold values [8]. Data contained in the project reports is available for use by industry to serve as a baseline for engineering evaluation tests, reducing the initial effort for ignition source prevention in fuel tank design. The work contained in these reports also serves an example of how testing and simulation can be paired to reduce the overall effort for compliance with §25.954.

8. Future Work

As the aircraft industry begins to incorporate welded thermoplastics into the structures, one area for future work related to this project is a study of the non-sparking fastener threshold for thermoplastic welded joints with reduced fastener quantities. Other interesting areas of analysis for future work are a computational model of current conducted through a composite and/or a composite-metal hybrid wing, and characterization of the edge glow phenomena in CFRPs.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] Federal Aviation Administration; Rules and Regulations; Transport Airplane Fuel Tank and System Lightning Protection, 83 Fed. Reg. 47548-47557, March 9, 2018
- [2] 14 CFR § 25.954
- [3] AC 25.954-1, U.S. Department of Transportation Federal Aviation Administration, "Transport Airplane Fuel System Lightning Protection" 2018
- [4] R. Khajepour, A. Gonzalez, M. Cronkleton, Y. Kostogorova-Beller, B. Martin, "Experimental Identification of Lightning Conducted-Current Fastener Sparking Thresholds (25.981 Project) – Test Results", Wichita State University – National Institute for Aviation Research, https://www.wichita.edu/industry_and_defense/NIAR/Documents/KART_25.981_Test_Report-Rev_A_Final.pdf 2021
- [5] SAE Aerospace ARP 5416A, SAE International, "Aircraft Lightning Test Methods" 2013
- [6] SAE Aerospace ARP 5412B, SAE International, "Aircraft Lightning Environment and Related Test Waveforms" 2013
- [7] SAE Aerospace ARP 5415B, SAE International, "User's Manual for Certification of Aircraft Electrical/Electronic Systems for the Indirect Effects of Lightning" 2020
- [8] R. Khajepour, A. Gonzalez, "KART 25.954 (25.981) Fastener Database Composite Report", Wichita State University – National Institute for Aviation Research, https://www.wichita.edu/industry_and_defense/NIAR/Documents/21-2152-RR52520Rev-Final.pdf 2021
- [9] A. Gonzalez, B. Martin, J. Phillips, "Incandescent Ignition Source Detection for Lightning Testing of Composite Structure" ICOLSE 2019

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Table 3. Test Article Abbreviation Sequence

A	Test article material/joint type	M-metal C-composite H-hybrid
B	Type of fastener installation	N-nominal F-fault
#	Type of fault	1-oversized hole 2-gap under head 3-gap under collar 4-scratch 5-burr 6-under-torque 7-countersink too deep 8-perpendicularity 9-substitute Hi-Kote
C	Number of fasteners per joint	1-single fastener 4-quadruple fasteners
D	Fastener fit type	I-interference T-transition 0-rivet installation C-clearance
E	Unique pin/collar combination	01-HL10VBJ5-3/ HL70-5 02-HL10VBJ8-3/ HL70-8 03-HL11VBJ5-3/ HL70-5 04-HL11VBJ8-3/ HL70-8 05-HST10BJ5-3/ HST79CY5 06-HST10BJ8-3/ HST79CY8 07-HST11BJ5-3/ HST79CY5 08-HST11BJ8-3/ HST79CY8 09-MS20470AD4 10-MS20470AD6 11-HST11AG5-3/ HST79CY5 12-HL11VAZ5-3/ HL70-5 18-HST10BJ8-5/ HST79CY8 19-HST10AG8-5/ HST79CY8 20-HST11BJ8-5/ HST79CY8 21-HST11AG8-5/ HST79CY8
F	Coupon type	A-ECF carbon skin to carbon internal structure C-ECF carbon with fiberglass to aluminum internal structure D-plain carbon skin with fiberglass to aluminum internal structure E-plain carbon skin to plain carbon internal structure
G	OEM Identifier	1-OEM 1 2-OEM 2 3-OEM 3 4-OEM 4 5-OEM 5

*Note: Phase 1 nominal test articles were abbreviated as: AB-CDE-G.

Phase 1 faulted test articles were abbreviated as: AB#-CDE-G.

Phase 3 nominal test articles were abbreviated as: AB-CDEF-G.

Phase 3 faulted test articles were abbreviated as AB#-CDEF-G.

Table 4. Phase 1 Fastener Configurations and Thresholds

Phase 1							
Metal Nominal				Metal Faults			
Single	Lowest Threshold (kV)	Quad	Lowest Threshold (kV)	Quad	Lowest Threshold (kV)	Quad	Lowest Threshold (kV)
MN-1I01	No Spark	MN-4I01	No Spark	MF1-4T01	32.97	MF5-4T12	4.239
MN-1I02	No Spark	MN-4I02	No Spark	MF1-4T03	18.4	MF6-4T01	28.5
MN-1I03	No Spark	MN-4I03	0.94	MF1-4T05	81.7	MF6-4T05	No Spark
MN-1I04	No Spark	MN-4I04	10.82	MF1-4T07	10.83	MF6-4T11	3.26
MN-1I05	No Spark	MN-4I05	No Spark	MF1-4T11	No Spark	MF6-4T12	4.23
MN-1I06	No Spark	MN-4I06	No Spark	MF1-4T12	0.16		
MN-1I07	No Spark	MN-4I07	No Spark	MF2-4T01	10.82		
MN-1I08	No Spark	MN-4I08	No Spark	MF2-4T05	13.97		
MN-1T01	No Spark	MN-4T01	10.79	MF3-4009	18.53		
MN-1T02	No Spark	MN-4T02	1078	MF3-4T01	10.84		
MN-1T03	No Spark	MN-4T03	10.8	MF3-4T05	10.8		
MN-1T04	No Spark	MN-4T04	No Spark	MF3-4T11	4.39		
MN-1T05	No Spark	MN-4T05	No Spark	MF3-4T12	4.32		
MN-1T06	No Spark	MN-4T06	No Spark	MF4-4009	13.73		
MN-1T07	No Spark	MN-4T07	No Spark	MF4-4T01	18.47		
MN-1T08	No Spark	MN-4T08	No Spark	MF4-4T05	61.53		
MN-1009	No Spark	MN-4009	No Spark	MF4-4T11	3.29		
MN-1010	No Spark	MN-4010	10.76	MF4-4T12	1.09		
MN-1I11	Not Obtained	MN-4I11	Not Obtained	MF5-4009	No Spark		
MN-1I12	Not Obtained	MN-4T11	No Spark	MF5-4T01	23.8		
MN-1T12	Not Obtained	MN-4I12	No Spark	MF5-4T05	10.8		
		MN-4T12	Not Obtained	MF5-4T11	3.25		

*Lowest threshold from across all OEMS is noted here. Some OEMs had higher threshold values for the same configurations

Table 5. Phase 3 Fastener Configurations and Thresholds

Phase 3							
Composite Nominal		Hybrid Nominal		Composite Faults		Hybrid Faults	
Quad	Threshold (kV)	Quad	Threshold (kV)	Quad	Threshold (kV)	Quad	Threshold (kV)
CN-4C18E	0.96	HN-4C18D	10.8	CF4-4C18E	6.4	HF4-4C18D	10.8
CN-4C19E	Not Obtained	HN-4C19D	5.36	CF4-4C20A	2.16	HF4-4C20C	10.8
CN-4C20A	10.16	HN-4C20C	31.1	CF5-4C18E	2.12	HF5-4C18D	10.8
CN-4C20E	44.1	HN-4C21C	20.73	CF5-4C20A	10.16	HF5-4C20C	10.8
CN-4C21A	10.24			CF6-4C18E	7.2	HF6-4C18D	10.8
CN-4C21E	18.2			CF6-4C20A	9.92	HF6-4C20C	20.93
				CF7-4C20A	10.24	HF7-4C20C	46.73
				CF8-4C18E	30.7	HF8-4C18D	10.8
				CF8-4C20A	10.24	HF8-4C20C	10.8
				CF9-4C18E	10.4	HF9-4C18D	10.8
				CF9-4C20A	10.16	HF9-4C20C	21.13